

Positionality Map

Adapted from Jacobson, D., & Mustafa, N. (2019). Social identity map: A reflexivity tool for practicing explicit positionality in critical qualitative research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 18, 1609406919870075.

Transformative Research Unit for Equity
Equity-Centered Methodology Tools